

PATHOGENETIC CLASSIFICATION OF ENURESIS

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ABSTRACT

This article illuminates the etiological factors and pathogenic mechanisms of enuresis. It analyzes the interplay of organic, functional, psychological, and genetic factors in the onset of enuresis. Furthermore, the main pathophysiological mechanisms of the disease's development are examined.

Introduction

Enuresis is a common pathological condition among children, characterized by involuntary urination during sleep. This problem is of not only medical but also psychological and social significance. To date, there is no single established theory on the origin of enuresis, which indicates its multifactorial nature.

Main Section

Etiology

The causes of enuresis are classified into several groups:

Organic factors: diseases of the urinary system (cystitis, pyelonephritis), central nervous system injuries, endocrine disorders

Functional factors: immaturity of the nervous system, an unformed urination reflex

Psychogenic factors: stress, fear, family problems

Genetic factors: hereditary predisposition

These factors often act in combination, leading to the development of enuresis.

Pathogenesis

The following mechanisms play a primary role in the development of enuresis:

inadequate formation of the arousal reflex when the bladder is full

impaired coordination between the central nervous system and urination reflexes

nocturnal polyuria resulting from decreased secretion of antidiuretic hormone (ADH)

bladder dysfunction (hyperreflexive or hyporeflexive states)

As a result, signals related to bladder fullness do not lead to awakening, and involuntary urination occurs.

Clinical forms

Enuresis is divided into the following forms:

Primary enuresis - continues from birth.

Secondary enuresis - appears again after a certain period of control.

Neurotic and neurosis-like forms

Urogenital, neurological and endocrine forms

Relevant importance

The current significance of enuresis is manifested in the following:

1. Psychological negative consequences: sleep disturbances in children, low self-esteem, problems of social adaptation at school.
2. Medical risks: chronic urinary tract infections, bladder and kidney dysfunction.
3. Socio-cultural issue: stigmatization and parental anxiety associated with the state of enuresis of the child in many families.
4. Necessity of prevention and treatment: with early diagnosis and an individual treatment approach, enuresis can be effectively controlled.

Therefore, a comprehensive approach in cooperation with pediatricians, neurologists, and psychologists is the most relevant method today.

Conclusion

Enuresis is a multifactorial disease in which the immaturity of the nervous system, hormonal imbalances, bladder dysfunction, and psychological factors play a significant role in its development. Therefore, an individualized approach to diagnosis and treatment is necessary.

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